

**ISSUES OF THEORETICAL DESCRIPTION OF REHABILITATION IN THE
CRIMINAL PROCESS IN THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES**

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The rehabilitation institute is developing and perfecting over time. Studying foreign experience in this field is important for improving the country's legislation. However, in this case, it is necessary to take into account the development features of the legislation of Uzbekistan and the legislation of any state. Otherwise, the changes introduced in the national legislation may not produce the expected result or have a negative impact on the field of legal relations under consideration. It is appropriate to study the experience of countries where the rehabilitation institute is established at the constitutional level, in codes or special laws. Because even in Uzbekistan, rehabilitation is reflected in the Criminal Procedure Code. The principles of compensation of damages and protection of citizens' rights are strengthened in many countries at the constitutional level. These countries include Japan, Switzerland, Romania, Poland, Portugal, Republic of Korea, China, Spain, Italy, Germany, Greece, Vietnam, Hungary, Brazil, Bulgaria, Austria, Albania, Azerbaijan, Algeria.

A. Yashina in his monograph states that despite the fact that these countries are at the level of ordinary legislation, they have perfectly reflected the above principles in their legislation and are improving it. In the countries of Albania, Vietnam, Guatemala and Honduras, the principle of compensation for damages, as well as the right of a citizen to rehabilitation, is established at the constitutional level. Of course, it is very correct to strengthen the institution of rehabilitation at the constitutional level, because it is considered to be the restoration of violated human rights. The criminal procedural codes of most of the CIS member states contain laws on compensation for damages caused to rehabilitated citizens. But Ukraine is considered an exception, and on December 1, 1994, Ukraine adopted a special law "On the procedure for compensation of damage caused to a citizen by illegal actions of the investigation, preliminary investigation, prosecutor's office and court." Rehabilitation norms are not included in the Criminal Procedure Code of Ukraine. There is no separate chapter on rehabilitation in the Criminal Procedure Code of Armenia. However, Article 22 of this Code is defined as "restoring the rights of persons affected by judicial errors". It mentions the restoration of the rights of the acquitted person and compensation for the damage

caused to him. This article obliges investigative bodies to take measures to restore the violated rights of citizens. In addition, the codex Article 66 defines the concept of an acquitted person and his rights. Article 7 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Belarus defines rehabilitation, full compensation for the damage, as well as restoration of rights violated as a result of illegal criminal prosecution as one of the tasks of the criminal procedure. However, the procedure for rehabilitation is not specified in the code. According to Article 465 of the Code, the body that conducted the criminal proceedings and is responsible for compensating the damage caused will officially apologize to this citizen. Chapter 48 of this code is entitled "Cases on compensation for damages caused by the illegal actions of the body conducting criminal proceedings". It reveals the concepts of physical, moral and property damage, as well as the concepts of violation of a person's labor, pension, housing and other personal property rights. It contains a list of persons entitled to claim compensation for the damage caused. Article 18 of the Hungarian Constitution "guarantees an impartial and fair trial within a certain period of time." The authorities are obliged to disclose the reasons for court verdicts. Every citizen has the right to claim compensation for illegal damage caused by authorities in the performance of their duties. A similar norm is reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Albanian constitution includes rights to rehabilitation and compensation. Article 44 of the Constitution states that "Anyone who has been harmed by the illegal action or inaction of state bodies has the right to be rehabilitated or released in accordance with the law." Article 9 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Albania stipulates the right to compensation and restitution of rights for persons who have been prosecuted illegally. The concept of rehabilitation is not included in the Polish constitution. However, the constitution guarantees that a person will be paid compensation for the damage caused as a result of the illegal actions of state authorities. Article 41 of the Constitution enshrines the right to compensation for damages caused to persons illegally deprived of their liberty. of the Constitution Article 77 stipulates that "no legal restriction may be placed on anyone preventing them from restoring their violated rights and freedoms through a court of law." The norm similar to the one in the above two countries is also reflected in the Constitution of Uzbekistan. However, there is no norm of payment of compensation for compensation of damage caused by state bodies to a person illegally. It is important that the activity of the state body that caused the damage is interpreted in a broad sense as any action or inaction, special measures, orders,

court decisions, administrative decisions, regulatory documents and legislative activity. The constitution of Kazakhstan does not provide for rehabilitation and compensation. However, Chapter 4 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Kazakhstan is devoted to rehabilitation. He "Rehabilitation. It is called compensation for damages caused by the illegal actions of the body conducting the criminal proceedings. The articles of the Code reveal the concept of partial and full rehabilitation. The circle of persons entitled to rehabilitation was announced, as well as the procedure for compensating the damage caused and the content of the property damage was revealed. Criminal Procedure Code of Turkmenistan Full and partial rehabilitation of a person is defined in Article 38. Article 41 of the Constitution of Turkmenistan provides for judicial compensation for material and moral damage caused by state bodies, organizations and individuals illegally. Also in the Criminal Procedure Code

Chapter 4 focuses on "compensation for damages caused by the illegal actions of the criminal prosecution body". The Vietnamese constitution, adopted on April 15, 1992, gives citizens the right to rehabilitation and compensation from the state. Article 72 of the Constitution states that "persons illegally detained, arrested, prosecuted, and found guilty of violation of the law have the right to receive compensation and rehabilitation." This provision allows rehabilitation of a person in criminal and administrative proceedings.

The Vietnamese constitution, adopted on April 15, 1992, gives citizens the right to rehabilitation and compensation from the state. Article 72 of the Constitution states that "persons illegally detained, arrested, prosecuted, and found guilty of violation of the law have the right to receive compensation and rehabilitation." This provision allows rehabilitation of a person in criminal and administrative proceedings. In Guatemala and Honduras, rehabilitation is regulated at the constitutional level. Article 20 of the Guatemalan Constitution of 1956 defines rehabilitation as one of the ways to restore a person's civil rights. Article 26 of the Honduran constitution, approved on March 28, 1936, provides for the restoration of the rights of citizens in the event of rehabilitation in accordance with the law. It should be noted that in both Guatemala and Honduras, rehabilitation is considered as a procedure for the re-socialization of persons who have served a sentence of deprivation of liberty.

From the above, it can be concluded that the constitutional legislation of some foreign countries has been improved in terms of the responsibility of the state authorities for the damage caused to the subjects of legal relations. There was no opportunity to prosecute the illegal actions of the first state bodies and officials.

Currently, in the legislation of foreign countries, there is a clear trend of compensating the damage caused by state bodies and officials at the expense of the state. Having studied the legislation of the aforementioned foreign countries, it is appropriate to reflect some of their aspects in our legislation.

Liberalization and improvement of criminal procedural legislation in the course of reforms in the field of justice is one of the priority tasks today. In order to implement these reforms and to develop and implement completely new mechanisms for improving criminal and criminal-procedural legislation, the Criminal and Criminal-Procedural Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3723 dated May 14, 2018 Concept of improvement of legislation was adopted. In this Concept, the task of improving certain institutions in crime and criminal process was determined.

According to him, it was emphasized that it is important to research the institution of "rehabilitation" in the criminal process and to create new methodological bases for the improvement of this institution, taking into account its specific features.

It is known that the rehabilitation institute serves to practically restore the violated rights and freedoms of citizens, recover all types of damages caused by illegal actions at the expense of the state, and restore the previous position of a person in society.

